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Relational model for the development of dynamic skills based on bibliometric analysis

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Abstract

This article exposes the formulation of a relational model that allows in any type of organization the practical development of the concepts proposed by the theory of Dynamic Capabilities, to be integrated as a management strategy that allows for increasing the levels of competitiveness and business survival, for which a qualitative study was carried out under the methodology of bibliometric analysis and documentary review of more than 500 relevant scientific documentary sources through an analytical and interpretive synthesis of the most significant arguments. Among the most important results of this study, it stands out the power to establish the most representative results of recent years, a relational model that identifies each of the steps and key factors that any type of organization must develop, to achieve the postulates that it exposes. The theory of dynamic capabilities is based on concepts such as organizational learning, absorbing knowledge, innovation, value-added, adaptability, business competitiveness, internationalization, and survival.

Keywords: Dynamic Capacities; innovation; internationalization; competitive advantage

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Modelo relacional para el desarrollo de habilidades dinámicas basado en análisis bibliométrico

Resumen

Este artículo expone la formulación de un modelo relacional que permita en cualquier tipo de organización el desarrollo práctico de los conceptos propuestos por la teoría de las Capacidades Dinámicas, para ser integrados como una estrategia de gestión que permita incrementar los niveles de competitividad y supervivencia empresarial, para el cual se realizó un estudio cualitativo bajo la metodología de análisis bibliométrico y revisión documental de más de 500 fuentes documentales científicas relevantes a través de una síntesis analítica e interpretativa de los argumentos más significativos. Entre los resultados más importantes de este estudio, destaca el poder establecer los resultados más representativos de los últimos años, un modelo relacional que identifica cada uno de los pasos y factores clave que debe desarrollar cualquier tipo de organización, para alcanzar los postulados que expone. La teoría de las capacidades dinámicas se basa en conceptos como el aprendizaje organizacional, la absorción de conocimiento, la innovación, el valor agregado, la adaptabilidad, la competitividad empresarial, la internacionalización y la supervivencia.

Palabras clave: capacidades dinámicas; innovación; internacionalización; ventaja competitiva.

1. Introduction

This article proposes as central research to highlight from an analysis of the state of the art with more than 70 first-order documentary sources, the need, and importance that it has today to implement the concepts that support the theory of dynamic capabilities, such as a fundamental strategic element to achieve better levels of business competitiveness. From this qualitative analysis, it is argued that the theory of dynamic capabilities is a strategic element that fosters the competitive development of any type of organization, to a greater extent than it is implemented as a management model that allows the development of new and

better processes that generate added value in today's business world.

In this sense, the most competitive companies on the planet have shown that the practical implementation of this set of concepts is an effective strategy to create scenarios that allow structuring models of learning and generation of new knowledge, because of efficient management of resources in the function of developing greater capacities that provide real solutions to the challenges imposed by the globalized market (Zhou et al, 2018). Therefore, the development of the theoretical concept of Resources and Capabilities initially formulated by Penrose (1959), which added to the managerial ability to create dynamic

capabilities, is undoubtedly a successful strategic alternative that promotes internal scenarios that drive the development of productive, technological, and innovation conditions with a sustainable economic approach (Chacón and Zapata, 2021).

It then means that the potential that public or private organizations have in any business sector after correctly applying these concepts is enormous, as it is a proposal that creates inclusive processes that significantly improve levels of competitiveness based on knowledge and resources. Company specific Porter et al, (2000). As pointed out by Acosta et al, (2013), Monferrer et al, (2013), and Helfat and Peteraf (2015), the development of dynamic capabilities effectively contributes not only to the competitive development of the company but also to the improvement of the socio-economic conditions of the external entities involved with the organization, as shown by the growth and poverty rates of countries such as Japan or China among others.

Likewise, it is noteworthy that through dynamic capabilities, organizations manage to promote new models of technological and social innovation that enable the creation of strategic alliances with customers, suppliers, distributors, competitors, and the community in general, to make management more efficient. of each of its resources with a competitive approach and even with a national and international scope (Yu and Kim, 2020). For these reasons that link the postulates of Barney (1991), Teece et al. (1997), Helfat and Peteraf (2003) and Cadrazco et al, (2020) among many others, the need arises to quickly adapt strategies that effectively promote tangible elements that improve the productive and competitive performance

of the organization, which begins with the missionary commitment to carry out a critical analysis of the current management model and the use of its resources and capacities for the creation of new added values.

For all the above, elaborating this type of analysis related to the topic of resources and capacities based on the development of dynamic capacities is of great use in the business and academic sphere, to the extent that it becomes an element of reflection on any of the new forms of competitive management that can be applied by organizations framed in achieving better performance within current local and international market conditions. Finally, this document aims to be an investigative instrument that promotes organizational learning processes in 21st-century companies based on one of the most relevant modern theories today in the face of the prevailing need to be more competitive, all within the variables of quality, productivity, and socioeconomic well-being with management models that guarantee sustainable growth.

2. Conceptualization of Dynamic Capabilities

The concept of Dynamic Capabilities refers to the potential of conditions that an organization has and on which decisions are made that allow adequate adaptability of the company to be able to competitively face both opportunities and threats from its environment, which is why today nowadays it is one of the main postulates on which the concept of strategic direction is structured (Miranda, 2015). The postulates on the theory of Dynamic Capabilities are based on the concepts initially proposed by Penrose (1959) in

his Theory of Resources and Capabilities as a factor that explains the phenomenon of business competitiveness.

To all these approaches, ideas such as business innovation (Schumpeter, 1997), Business Capabilities (Nelson and Winter, 1982), Resources and Capabilities (Teece, 1982; Teece, 2009), Development of Competitive Capabilities (Barney, 1991), Combined Abilities (Kogut and Zander, 1992) and Configuration of Competences (Henderson and Cockburn, 1994) among others. Based on this set of knowledge, Teece et al, (1997) merge the theory of Resources and Capabilities with their analyses to formulate the current concept of Dynamic Capabilities, which focuses on creating long-term strategies that allow achieving performance organizational superiority over that of competitors, an aspect also analyzed by Chen and Jaw (2009) and Lew et al. (2013).

Therefore, it is vitally important to be able to identify in an organization what its capabilities are and what factors drive them towards competitive performance, to the extent that stronger capabilities are better dynamized as competitive advantages that allow them to adequately face threats and efficiently take advantage of the opportunities that exist in the market (Vicente et al, 2018). In this sense, as expressed by Vesalainen and Hakala (2004) and Cadrazco et al, (2020), dynamic capabilities allow determining to a large extent the speed of reaction with which an organization can design value-creating strategies through its performance and align itself competitively against each of the needs or conditions imposed by the current globalized world of business.

This perspective is based on efficient management of resources and the capabilities that can be

generated from them, which allows the development of a strategic formulation that is the key element to improving the levels of competitiveness and therefore profitability of the company (Penrose, 1959). Therefore, Dynamic Capabilities are based on creating competitive advantages from strategies that allow taking better advantage of the differences in the added value that represent the characteristics of the organization, doing so in an adaptive way in the face of changing conditions in the business environment (Acosta et al, 2013; Sijabat et al., 2021).

In this regard, Amit and Schoemaker (1993) emphasize that resources should be considered stocks of available factors that generate capabilities that must be managed and controlled efficiently by the company, which means that capabilities are faculties that can be created through proper management of resources based on production and administrative processes. Added to the above is the definition provided by Grant (1991) inferring that capabilities are the set of skills that an organization has when efficiently combining its resources to productively develop a specific task, concluding that resources are the source of capabilities, and these are the fundamental basis of competitive advantage through processes, products, goods, or services.

From this analysis, Thorbjørn and Madsen (2002) establish that to achieve the competitive goal that any organization imposes, resources must be analyzed from an internal strategic approach that, added to the identification of opportunities in the environment allow managing which capacities must be developed; that is perceived as added value, especially in globalized economies or open markets where developing dynamic capabilities

has become a vital element since it offers a strategic management model that facilitates adaptability to changes in the environment.

Similarly, Albort et al, (2016) and Escandon et al, (2013) point out that based on the resources and capabilities approach, it is possible to manage strategies that lead to the generation of values that are perceived as truly competitive, which must be permanently reevaluated so that they can be dynamic based on changes, imposed by the globalized market environment,

organizational learning, and innovation processes, among others.

To facilitate the understanding of the concept that encompasses dynamic capabilities, Chart 1 below presents a survey of the most relevant and representative definitions in the disciplinary field, clarifying in advance that the existing literature on the subject is widely heterogeneous and that therefore, it is complex to establish an argumentative consensus that defines a single.

Chart 1
Main definitions of Dynamic Capabilities

Authors	Definition of Dynamic Capabilities
Schumpeter (1939)	Capacity for innovation, architect of the process of creative destruction, associated with characteristics that entrepreneurs have and that are key to the process of continuous change.
Nelson (1991)	The evolution of essential capabilities is built on a hierarchical basis of organizational routines, which are defined within an evolutionary context.
Collis (1994)	It refers to the ability to develop and innovate processes in the company faster than competitors.
Teece and Pisano (1994)	Ability to take advantage of resources and organizational processes to generate new competitive strategies in a market environment.
Schumpeter (1997)	He starts from the innovative factor in the production processes and the ability to modify processes to improve them, for which they are considered dynamic.
Helfat (1997)	A subset of skills that allows the company to create new processes and products, as well as respond to changing circumstances in the environment.
Teece et al (1997)	The ability of the company to integrate, build and reconfigure internal and external skills to respond on time to the environment.
Eisenhardt and Martin (2000)	Organizational strategy with which the company achieves new configurations of resources to emerge in the market.
Helfat and Raubitschek (2000)	The ability of the organization to innovate and adapt to changes in factors such as technology and markets is based on learning from mistakes for continuous improvement of processes.
Makadok (2001)	Processes from which companies generate economic rents by being more competitive than their rivals when deploying resources.

Cont... Chart 1

Lee et al (2002)	A new source of competitive advantage where is conceptualized how organizations are capable of adapting to the changes required by the environment.
Zahra and George (2002)	Capabilities that help organizations replace and configure their resources to meet customer demands with competitive strategies.
Zollo and Winter (2002)	The learned pattern establishes a systematic activity in the company that allows modifying its operational routines to improve its competitiveness.
Helfat and Peteraf (2003)	It is the capacity that adaptation and change imply from integrating and reconfiguring resources and abilities.
Winter (2003)	Capabilities that operate to be able to modify and create more competitive organizational skills.
Zahra et al (2006)	Ability to adapt the resources and processes of the company in such a way that it is the best option for decision-makers within the company.
Teece (2007)	It is the ability to create intangible assets that support superior performance in the long term, intending to develop new products and processes within business models that are more viable, flexible, and adaptable to the environment.
Wang and Ahmed (2007)	Continued integration, reconfiguration, renewal, and regeneration of the firm's resources and capabilities. It is the augmentation and rebuilding of your essential capabilities in dynamic environments to gain a competitive advantage.
Augier and Teece (2007)	The inimitable capacity that a company has to form and configure its asset base, to respond to changes generated in markets and technologies.
McKelvie and Davidsson (2009)	Abilities that a company has to integrate and change the resource base in the face of changes that occur in the environment. They are integrated and transformed processes to generate new activities and create value for the organization.
Barreto (2010)	Potential that the company has to systematically solve a problem, by identifying opportunities and threats, with market-oriented decisions.
Teece (2009)	They are high-level skills that determine the ability of a company to integrate, build and reconfigure internal and external resources so that it can face the market dynamically. It is the speed and scope with which the organization's resources can be aligned to take advantage of business opportunities and generate sustainable income in the long term.
Vivas (2013)	High-level processes that are responsible for providing the appropriate conditions for the modification and renewal of the organization's assets.
Helfat and Peteraf (2015)	Dynamic capabilities arise from managers with superior cognitive abilities, who seek to create competitive advantages so that the company reacts promptly and takes advantage of opportunities.
Zapata and Mirabal (2018)	The dynamic ability of an organization to change and reconfigure the substantive capabilities of its business denotes the ability to modify how it responds to the changing needs of the environment.

Source: Self-made (2022)

In recent decades, organizations have been immersed in permanent change processes to strengthen their production and administrative processes to achieve higher levels of competitiveness, which is why they must structure plans and strategies that promote the development of dynamic capabilities from four forms or categories that are (Stulova and Rungi, 2017; Wendra et al, 2019):

a) *Organizational Learning Capabilities*, which are also recognized by Garzón (2015) under the name of Strategic Capabilities to the extent that they are supported in the development of processes that allow a strategic redesign of a higher order that allows a more competitive business model, based on in elements such as innovation, technology, better resources, assets, business alliances and new forms of negotiation (Batra et al, 2015; Saha et al, 2020; Sawers et al, 2008).

b) *Absorption Capabilities*, refer to the condition through which the company internalizes new knowledge generated from its interaction with the environment and other organizations, all under a structured approach to learning for continuous improvement (Cohen and Levinthal, 1990; Lane and Lubatkin, 1998).

c) *The Innovation Capabilities* are those skills that the organization creates from research, creativity, and the generation of new own knowledge, which allows the development of competitive strategies based on the innovation of processes, products, or services, which represent factors of change and competitive adaptability in the market

(Carattoli, 2013; López and Montero, 2012; Sasmoko et al, 2019).

d) *The Adaptation Capacity*, which is based on the organization's way of managing and competitively adapting its resources and conditions to the new market demands, implies the design of transformation strategies that allow efficient use of the opportunities offered by each environment. In this sense, Teece et al, (1997), and Stam and Elfring (2008) postulate the great need for organizations to focus administrative and productive efforts on the development of real capacities that allow correct flexibility of their production processes, to guarantee a rapid adaptation to changes that the environment demands; and for which the creation of strategic alliances that facilitate this sustainable condition is of vital help.

3. Elements Methodological

The investigative development of this article was carried out through the documentary review process based on bibliometric analysis of scientific publications associated with the subject of dynamic capacities, to be able to carry out an evolutionary evaluation and interpretation of results that allow establishing conclusions supported in disciplinary arguments (Merigó et al, 2016). To carry out this work, in the first instance a search equation was designed that would include in the Scopus databases the terms considered as key elements that directly link the concepts of greatest interest that are intended to be covered in this research (Chart 2).

Chart 2 Bibliographic Search Criteria

Search Equation	title-abs-key (capability* and dynamic*) and (innovation* or novation) and (internationalization or globalization) or (influence or impact or relation or effect)) and (company or business or organization or industry or establishment)) and (exclude (pubstage,"aip")) and (exclude (doctype,"no") or exclude (doctype,"tb")) and (limit-to (subarea,"busi"))
Knowledge Area	Business, Management, and Accounting
Document Types	Papers, conferences, conference reviews, books, book chapters, and reviews
Time Frame	1988 - 2021

Source: Self-made (2022)

The total relevant results found in the present search were 511 documents, of which 396 correspond to articles of a scientific nature, 55 conference documents, 37 book chapters, 9 books, 7 conferences and 7 bibliographic reviews, written then in 98.8% are in English. Subsequently, using *VOSViewer software*, it is observed that bibliometric results allow building a network analysis and concurrence of scientific literature, which was held around the criteria of keywords, year of publication, country, authors, and citation, which can be seen in the next apart.

4. Bibliometric analysis and relational model for the development of dynamic skills

From the methodological application of this research, a bibliometric analysis was initially obtained that shows a growing trend in the number of scientific publications associated with the subject of study and its relationship with the processes of business competitiveness, where the United States stands out as the country with the largest number of documents, with a total of 9,874 references and a

binding force of 134 articles, highlighting the articles by Benner and Tushman (2003) with 2,237 citations and that of Rothaermel and Hess (2007) with 509. Similarly, publications of Spanish origin with 1,676 references and a link strength of 35, the United Kingdom with 1,421 citations with a link of 40, and Germany with 1,259 citations and a link strength of 29 are observed to a lesser extent.

When analyzing the co-citations, which is a semantic measure that measures the frequency with which articles are cited in other documents, it is found that the most important publication is Business models and dynamic capabilities by Teece (2018) with 621 citations and a force link of 12,211. Likewise, there are other articles with high levels of citation such as Understanding dynamic capabilities by Winter (2003) with 292 citations and a binding force of 8,345; Dynamic capabilities: What are they? by Eisenhardt and Martin (2000) with 291 citations and a link of 5,969; Toward a prescriptive theory of dynamic capabilities: connecting strategic choice, learning, and competition by Pisano (2017) with 255 citations and a link of 5,659; and Orchestrating the new dynamic capabilities by Shuen and

Sieber (2009) with 245 citations and a link of 4,916.

Extending the results of the bibliometric analysis, only since 2014 are studies focused on new aspects such as organizational learning, knowledge management, and innovation, the latter being the most frequent topic of research and therefore scientific publications with a total of 174 significant documents. In this same line of research, it is highlighted that only after the year 2016 it is observed that the analysis of the theory of dynamic capacities, absorption capacities, innovation capacities, intellectual capital, human capital, and innovation emerge as a central theme of study. This same result is found in 2018 where important research related to the

issues of sustainability, entrepreneurship, and innovative business models linked to the theory of Dynamic Capabilities as elements that generate long-term competitive advantages is observed.

Through Diagram 1, the set of interrelationships that arise from the analysis of keywords of the publications under study can be identified, with the main result that the topics with the greatest frequency and relevance in the investigative works are the capacities dynamics and innovation. Likewise, in shades of yellow, other topics with remarkable research intensity are highlighted, among which knowledge management, internationalization, and absorption capacities stand out.

Diagram 1
Co-occurrence analysis based on keywords

Source: The authors (2022).

Subsequently, after performing a co-occurrence analysis of the publications, 5 different clusters are identified in Diagram 2 as relevant, where dynamic capabilities, innovation, human capital, and competitive advantage

stand out in red with 27 different themes as the most important due to their scale of frequency. The second most significant cluster that can be displayed in the green this group has 12 thematic items that refer to innovation capacities,

According to most of the studies included in this research, innovation processes are recognized as the transversal element with the greatest positive relationship in terms of the development of Dynamic Capabilities, allowing organizations to better react to market changes and rapid technological adaptation, which facilitates the development of products and implementation of business models (Chiva et al, 2014; Santos-Vijande et al, 2012; Teece, 2007; Wang and Ahmed, 2007).

In this context, in almost all the studies, the implementation of the concepts associated with the knowledge management theory is demonstrated as central support for the achievement of dynamic capacities, to the extent that it provides the basic guidelines for the development of organizational activities focused on the generation, appropriation, accumulation and application of new knowledge as a source of added value and competitive advantages (Ilmudeen et al, 2019; Rodríguez et al, 2011).

In this order of ideas, it can be inferred that knowledge management by the company is a directly proportional factor in the generation of wealth in terms of economic profitability, innovation, and sustainability, as a consequence of organizational learning materialized in competitiveness within its market environment that allows better positioning by developing innovations focused on the needs of its customers (Abdul-Halim et al , 2019; Garzón, 2015; Spender and Grant, 1996).

Likewise, after analyzing the results, it is evident that the objective of developing dynamic capabilities should be focused on achieving high-

level innovation processes since it is interpreted as the factor that generates the greatest competitive ability for the company, a factor that can be promoted through Strategic Alliances. To introduce innovative products and services, focus efforts on achieving learning and adaptation capabilities that allow the true needs of the market to be correctly identified and interpreted under a focus on full customer satisfaction and competitiveness with international standards (Berends et al, 2016; Calantone et al, 2002; Eisenhardt and Martin, 2000).

As a result of this study, a Relational Model is proposed for the development of Dynamic Capabilities that exposes the type of dependencies and process order that the organization must generate for the development of competitive skills and internationalization (Graphic 3).

This model requires a logical and systematic process to follow for the development of each of the capabilities of **Organizational Learning OLC01** (Human Resources HR1 + Organizational Culture OC2 + Intellectual Capital IC3 + External Knowledge Competence EKC4), **Absorption AC02** (Opportunity Detection OD5 + External Knowledge of the Market EKM6 + Assimilation of Learning AL7), **Innovation IC03** (Value Creation VC8 + Organizational Development OD9 + Organizational Skills OS10), and **Adaptation ADC04** (Corporate Strategy CS11 + Sustainability SUS12 + Performance Organization PO13 + Market Expansion ME14) like elements that generate competitiveness, survival, and internationalization.

Graphic 3
Relational Model of Dynamic Capabilities

Source: Self-made (2022)

5. Conclusions

The efficient use of resources and the generation of new knowledge for the development of greater capacities that become more dynamic in the face of the organization's needs is one of the best ways to detect opportunities for change and favorable conditions to compete in an ever-increasing market globalized. That is why it is unquestionable that the theory of Dynamic Capabilities is currently one of the most relevant issues for the development of new processes, added values, and competitive advantages in the local and international business environment, which is why the formation of new research processes should be

promoted in a field of knowledge that turns out to be of great relevance both in academic terms and in management in any type of organization.

The importance and need to create in all types of companies' research processes that allow identifying the possibility of really structuring the concept of dynamic capabilities is specified, for which establishing alliances with other organizations and particularly with universities turns out to be an efficient strategy in terms of time, costs and results. Unfortunately, in environments such as Latin America, the creation of strategic alliances between academic institutions or specialized research centers turns out to be very few, which

does not allow taking advantage of the broad business potential and the benefits that joint work between institutions of the real productive sector would generate both in the public and private sphere.

It is evident through this research that organizational learning processes and knowledge generation are the most important elements in the development of dynamic capabilities because they are factors that translate into basic elements that support the strategies of any organization and promote the continuous improvement of both production and management processes. Therefore, investing in organizational learning processes should be a priority for companies to the extent that it allows better adaptation to market changes and the identification of exploitable opportunities based on internal capabilities and alliances with other companies.

In the case of companies that are interested in achieving internationalization processes, dynamic capabilities are the catalyst for productive and management efforts that create the ideal conditions to be able to market products and/or services internationally under the conditions required by the market. It means that the development of dynamic capacities allows to correctly adapt the management of resources and the creation of competitive business skills that give an effective response to each of the needs posed by international markets, with greater adaptability to make changes in terms of processes, products or services both strategically and operationally and achieve the satisfaction of new customers and consumers.

Considering the proposal of the relational model to achieve the development of dynamic capacities, it

is considered necessary for companies to join forces through strategic alliances so that they promote a mutually favorable exchange of both resources and capacities that promote knowledge management, to the extent possible. That is identified as the key element and that represents the greatest limitation to achieving this condition of business success. In this sense, the learning and generation of new knowledge integrated into the processes of the organization is the main task, so facilitating access to new external knowledge allows the creation of competitive advantages for the development of innovations of all kinds as a vital factor to retain and generate clients in any local or international field of business.

On the other hand, based on the results obtained from the review of the specialized literature and the bibliometric analysis, it is established that the subject of dynamic capabilities has a large number of investigations focused mostly on two arguments that are Innovation and Knowledge Management, aspects that although they are positive in terms of relevant scientific production in the field of organizations, result in several repetitive aspects given the focus of the publications observed. Therefore, it is time to raise the need to analyze the concept of dynamic capabilities theory from other fields of knowledge different from those already existing, given that their contributions will be equally relevant for the development of new management models, production processes, and generation of resources, knowledge applied to the context of competitiveness.

Finally and based on the above, the formulation of new lines of research is proposed in several of the less explored topics according to the documentary analysis carried out,

so that studies based on factors such as environmental management, the generation of Knowledge through social innovation, new models of a selection of human talent or models of sustainable development, are works that can have a great impact as factors that allow explaining the development of dynamic competitive capacities both locally and internationally.

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